

Notas breves

Emilio, a replacement name for *Carinatus* Rubio & Rolán, 2020 (Mollusca: Gastropoda: Vitrinellidae)

Emilio, nombre sustituto para *Carinatus* Rubio & Rolán, 2020 (Mollusca: Gastropoda: Vitrinellidae)

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We have recently been kindly alerted by Tony Rees that the generic name *Carinatus* Rubio & Rolán, 2020, proposed for a genus of the family Vitrinellidae (RUBIO & ROLÁN, 2020), was preoccupied by the fossil Crustacean genus *Carinatus* Nyborg, Phillips, Van Bakel & Vega, 2017 (NYBORG ET AL., 2017). Therefore, *Carinatus* Rubio & Rolán, 2020 is a junior homonym and must be replaced in order to fulfil the requirements of Art. 23 of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature.

We here propose *Emilio* nom. nov. (urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:25739FE7-8107-44EB-B903-5CD002893CAE) as replacement name for *Carinatus* Rubio & Rolán, 2020, named after our good colleague Emilio Rolán Álvarez, son of the second author. This change results in the following new combinations for the type species *Carinatus regius* and the remaining ones described by RUBIO & ROLÁN (2020):

Emilio regius (Rubio & Rolán, 2020), comb. nov., type species.

Emilio bicarinatus (Rubio & Rolán, 2020), comb. nov.

Emilio fijiensis (Rubio & Rolán, 2020), comb. nov.

Emilio gracilis (Rubio & Rolán, 2020), comb. nov.

Emilio ministriatus (Rubio & Rolán, 2020), comb. nov.

Emilio obesus (Rubio & Rolán, 2020), comb. nov.

Emilio simplex (Rubio & Rolán, 2020), comb. nov.

Emilio variabilis (Rubio & Rolán, 2020), comb. nov.

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RUBIO F. & ROLÁN E. 2020. *Carinatus*, a new genus for the family Vitrinellidae (Gastropoda, Truncatelloidea) from the Pacific Ocean, with the description of 8 new species. *Xenophora Taxonomy*, 30: 47-54.